

D6.2. Definition and integration of demographic base submodels

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
ESP	Spain
ACs	Autonomous Communities

SUMMARY

This document describes the demographic projection system implemented in the SPANDAM local simulation model. The SPANDAM model simulates the demographic evolution of an area or region consisting of a number of municipalities. As it is a model that is fundamentally oriented towards the problem of rural depopulation, this region will most of the time be characterised by a low population size. For this reason, some of the inputs of the projection model are taken from the scenarios elaborated for Spain and the Autonomous Communities, while others are specific to the region to be projected.

The document is divided into two sections. The first section describes the general projection model and the algorithms used to calculate the demographic projection of a region. The second section describes how the various inputs to the projection model are obtained.

LOCAL PROJECTION MODEL AND CALCULATION ALGORITHMS

The local population projection was made using the components method, which is based on the classic compensating equation that explains the growth or decline of a population over a period as a function of the demographic phenomena that determine its evolution.

The approach of the method is generational, since it projects the future evolution of the population of the different cohorts. For those cohorts that are present at the initial moment of the projection, those who die or emigrate are subtracted and those who immigrate during the projection period are added. At the same time, births occurring during the years being projected are estimated, and we proceed in the same way, subtracting those who die or emigrate and adding those who emigrate. In the model, deaths, births and emigrants depend on the population and, therefore, are estimated from rates applied to the population of the cohorts, while immigrants are considered as absolute values to be added to the population of the different cohorts.

1.1. NOMENCLATURE

Numbers		Rates	
P	population		
N	births	f	fertility
D	deaths	m	mortality
I	immigrants		
E	emigrants	e	emigration

Variables	Subindexes and values	
Year	t	
Territory	AC	Autonomous Community
	R	region (set of municipalities)
Sex	s	
	m	man
	f	women
Age	x	
		simple age 0 to 100+
		Starting population up to 100+
		Results 99+ (effective events)
		100+ (effective populations)
Birth cohort	c	
		n corresponds to births, is the corresponding year in each projection year.

Time reference of data

Population data refer to January 1 of each year, while demographic phenomena cover the entire year, from January 1 to December 31 of each year.

1.2. INPUTS FROM MODEL

Starting population	$P_{T,s,x}^{t_0}$	R	$x = 0, 1, \dots, 99, 100+$
Mortality	$mm_{T,s,x}^t$	ACs	$x = n, 0, 1, \dots, 98, 99+$
Fertility	$ff_{T,f,x}^t$	ACs	$x = 14, 15, \dots, 49$
Emigration	$ee_{T,s,x}^t$	R, ACs	$x = n, 0, 1, \dots, 98, 99+$
Immigration	$Ii_{T,s,x}^t$	R, ACs	$x = n, 0, 1, \dots, 98, 99+$

1.3. CENTRAL FORMULAS

1.3.1. CALCULATION OF BIRTHS

To calculate births, the year-cohort fertility rates of the Autonomous Communities applied to the female population of childbearing age in the region. The calculation formulas are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x = 15 \quad N_{R,f,15}^t &= \left(\frac{P_{R,f,14}^t + P_{R,f,15}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * ff_{AC,f,14}^t + \left(\frac{P_{R,f,15}^t + P_{R,f,16}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{ff_{AC,f,15}^t}{2} \\
 x = 16-48 \quad N_{R,f,x}^t &= \left(\frac{P_{R,f,x-1}^t + P_{R,f,x}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{ff_{AC,f,x-1}^t}{2} + \left(\frac{P_{R,f,x}^t + P_{R,f,x+1}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{ff_{AC,f,x}^t}{2} \\
 x = 49 \quad N_{R,f,49}^t &= \left(\frac{P_{R,f,48}^t + P_{R,f,49}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{ff_{AC,f,48}^t}{2} + \left(\frac{P_{R,f,49}^t + P_{R,f,50}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * ff_{AC,f,49}^t
 \end{aligned}$$

Finally, births are totalled by mother's age and distributed by sex based on a Birth Masculinity Index (IMN, currently 0.5168).

$$N_{R,m}^t = IMN * \sum_{x=15}^{49} N_{R,f,x}^t \quad N_{R,f}^t = (1 - IMN) * \sum_{x=15}^{49} N_{R,f,x}^t$$

1.3.2. CALCULATION OF THE POPULATION N

Population aged 0 years

$$P_{R,s,0}^{t+1} = \frac{[1 - 0,5 * (mm_{AC,s,n}^t + ee_{R,s,n}^t)] * N_{R,s}^t + Ii_{R,s,n}^t}{[1 + 0,5 * (mm_{AC,s,n}^t + ee_{R,s,n}^t)]}$$

Population aged 1-99 years

$$P_{R,S,x+1}^{t+1} = \frac{[1 - 0,5 * (mm_{AC,S,x}^t + ee_{R,S,x}^t)] * P_{R,S,x}^t + II_{R,S,x}^t}{[1 + 0,5 * (mm_{AC,S,x}^t + ee_{R,S,x}^t)]}$$

Open group population

$$P_{R,S,100+}^{t+1} = \frac{[1 - 0,5 * (mm_{AC,S,99+}^t + ee_{R,S,99+}^t)] * (P_{R,S,99}^t + P_{R,S,100+}^t) + II_{R,S,99+}^t}{[1 + 0,5 * (mm_{AC,S,99+}^t + ee_{R,S,99+}^t)]}$$

1.3.3. CALCULATION OF DEMOGRAPHIC EVENTS

In the projection model, deaths and emigrants are obtained by cohort-period, which requires a subsequent transformation to obtain them classified by age and year of projection. This transformation is carried out using the formulas:

$$x = 0 \quad Z_{R,S,0}^t = \left(\frac{N_{R,S}^t + P_{R,S,0}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * tt_{T,S,n}^t + \left(\frac{P_{R,S,0}^t + P_{R,S,1}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{tt_{T,S,0}^t}{2}$$

$$x = 1-98 \quad Z_{R,S,x}^t = \left(\frac{P_{R,S,x-1}^t + P_{R,S,x}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{tt_{T,S,x-1}^t}{2} + \left(\frac{P_{R,S,x}^t + P_{R,S,x+1}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{tt_{T,S,x}^t}{2}$$

$$x = 99+ \quad Z_{R,S,99+}^t = \left(\frac{P_{R,S,98}^t + P_{R,S,99}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{tt_{T,S,98}^t}{2} + \left(\frac{P_{R,S,99}^t + P_{R,S,100+}^t + P_{R,S,100+}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{tt_{T,x,99+}^t}{2}$$

with: tt	Z
mm	D
ee	E

where T = AC for mortality, and T = R for emigration.

HYPOTHESIS

Mortality and fertility rates are exogenous to the model and correspond to three scenarios of future developments for Spain and its Autonomous Communities developed in the framework of the SPANDAM project (see deliverable 6.1). In contrast, immigrants and emigration rates are endogenous to the model, and are based on the values observed in the region projected in recent years.

1.1. MORTALITY AND FERTILITY

The mortality and fertility inputs correspond to the corresponding cohort rates projected in the medium and long-term demographic scenarios for Spain and the Autonomous Communities:

$$mm_{AC,s,x}^t$$

$$ff_{AC,f,x}^t$$

where t is the year, s is the sex, f are the woman, x is the age and AC is the Autonomous Community.

Note. Most of the projected regions will be made up of municipalities in the same Autonomous Community, and the fertility and mortality rates of that community will be applied directly. However, the model also allows the projection of a region made up of municipalities from two or more Autonomous Communities. In this case, the mortality and fertility inputs applied to the region are calculated as the average of the values of the respective Autonomous Communities, weighted by the demographic weight that the municipalities of each Autonomous Community have in the whole of the region to be projected.

1.2. MIGRATION

1.2.1. EMIGRATION

The emigration rates inputs for the region are calculated endogenously. The starting point is the synthetic emigration index by sex (ISM). The ISM is the sum of the emigration rates of all cohorts by sex that has been observed historically in the last five years in the region, and the value of the aggregate indicator of population attractiveness at the starting point of the simulation. It is assumed that if the aggregate indicator of population attractiveness remains constant, the synthetic emigration index will also remain constant. If the value of the aggregate indicator of population attractiveness varies, so does the synthetic emigration index.

$$ISM_{R,s}^t = ISM_{R,s}^{t_0} + \varphi \cdot (AI_R^t - AI_R^{t_0})$$

Where t is the year, ISM is the synthetic emigration index, AI is the Aggregate Indicator of population attractiveness and φ is the parameter that regulates how much the variation of the aggregate indicator affects the synthetic emigration index.

Once the synthetic emigration index by sex has been found, an age distribution is established by multiplying the synthetic index of emigration of each sex by an age pattern of emigrants. The relative patterns of emigration have been calculated for each sex with the data observed for the last five years at the Autonomous Community level. This gives the emigration rate by sex and cohort used above.

$$ee_{R,s,c}^t = ISM_{R,s}^t * \%ee_{AC,s,c}^{2015-2019}$$

Where, t is the year, ISM is the synthetic emigration index, $\%ee$ is the relative pattern of out-migration by cohort, s is the sex, c is the cohort, R is the region and AC is the Autonomous Community.

1.2.2. IMMIGRATION

The immigration values inputs for the region are calculated endogenously. This time the starting point is the immigration rate in the last five years and the value of the aggregate indicator of population attractiveness at the initial time of the simulation. It is assumed that if the aggregate indicator of population attractiveness remains constant, the immigration rate will also remain constant. If the aggregate indicator of population attractiveness varies, so does the immigration rate. The calculation of the total number of immigrants can be expressed as follows

$$I_R^t = [i_R^{t_0} + \omega \cdot (AI_R^t - AI_R^{t_0})] \cdot \sum_{x,s} P_{R,x,s}^t$$

Where t is the year, I is the total number of immigrants, i is the immigration rate, $\sum_{x,s} P_{R,x,s}^t$ is the total population of the region and ω is the parameter that regulates how much the variation of the AI of population attractiveness affects the immigration rate.

Once the total number of immigrants has been calculated, they are distributed by sex according to the ratio of male to female immigration observed in the region in recent years.

$$I_{R,m}^t = I_R^t \cdot \frac{I_{R,m}^{2015-2019}}{I_R^{2015-2019}}$$

$$I_{R,f}^t = I_R^t \cdot \left(1 - \frac{I_{R,m}^{2015-2019}}{I_R^{2015-2019}}\right)$$

Finally, the total immigrants of each sex are distributed by cohorts according to the relative pattern of immigration observed in recent years in their Autonomous Community.

$$ii_{R,s,c}^t = I_{R,s}^t * \%ii_{AC,s,c}^{2015-2019}$$

Where t is the year, I is the total number of immigrants, $\%ii$ is the relative pattern of immigration, R is the region, AC the Autonomous Community, s is the sex and c the cohort.